

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with 1-Amino-2-Naphthol-4-Sulphonic Acid and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Nine mixed-ligand complexes of the type $[ML_2B_2]$ where $M = \text{Co(II)}$, Cu(II) and Zn(II) . $\text{LH} = 1\text{-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid}$ and B is nitrogen donor ligand like quinoline, pyridine, gamma-picoline and diethylamine have been synthesised and characterised as octahedral complexes on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR and electronic spectral data.

In our attempt to synthesise complexes of unusual coordination number, we have been trying for the base adduct formation of some divalent metal chelates. Several such base adducts of beta-diketonates and beta-ketoesters of Zn(II) and Cu(II) have been reported earlier¹⁻³. It was therefore thought worthwhile to extend our investigation to the synthesis of some mixed-ligand complexes using 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid as the chelating ligand.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metal chelates were prepared by usual manner by reacting metal chlorides (Cobalt chloride 2.36 g, Copper chloride 1.69 g and zinc chloride 1.36 g) with ethanolic solution of 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (4.7 g) followed by the dropwise addition of ammonia. The compounds thus formed were suction filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Metal chelates were suspended in ethanol, mixed with the nitrogen donor ligands in 1 : 2 ratio and the mixture refluxed for about 1 hr., when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling the solution, crystalline compounds separated out. These were filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried in vacuo.

Metal contents in the complexes were estimated by complexometric E.D.T.A. method and nitrogen by standard micro analytical method. Conductance was measured in $M/1000$ DMF solution of the complexes using Toshniwal's conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using chloroform base solution of the complexes by Hilger-Watt UVSPECK spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy method using

$\text{Co}[\text{Hg}(\text{SCN}_4)]$ as calibrant. Relevant analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and IR spectral data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition $[ML_2B_2]$ where $M = \text{Co(II)}$, Cu(II) and Zn(II) ; $\text{LH} = 1\text{-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid}$ and B is a nitrogen donor ligand like quinoline, pyridine, gamma-picoline and diethylamine. Cobalt(II) complexes are brown, copper(II) complexes are green and zinc(II) complexes are white in colour. All the nine complexes have fairly low melting points and low conductance values in DMF indicating non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment values show the presence of three and one unpaired electron in case of cobalt and copper complexes respectively and indicate a spin-free octahedral configuration for the cobalt and copper compounds.

The IR spectra of metal chelates and the corresponding base adducts are informative. Here 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid can function as a bidentate chelating ligand using the hydroxyl oxygen and the primary amino nitrogen atom as the bonding sites, the sulphonic acid group remaining free probably due to steric reasons and spatial position. The C-O stretching vibrations in alcohols usually occur⁴ in $1260\text{-}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region which has appeared in the ligand at 1220 cm^{-1} and shifted to $\sim 1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the metal chelates indicating bonding of the oxygen atom. In the base-adducts, this band again shifts to higher frequency regions appearing at 1210 cm^{-1} indicating the bonding of the oxygen atom to the metal ion $\nu(\text{N-H})$ in the chelating ligand appears at 3250 cm^{-1} as a sharp peak. In the metal chelates and base-adducts N-H stretching frequency appears either as a broad band or is split into several peaks not so sharp as in the parent compound proving indirect evidence for

TABLE-1 ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	M.P. (°C)	% Metal		% N		μ_{eff} B.M.	$\Delta mhos$ cm^{-2}	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(N-H)$	$\nu(M-O)$	$\nu(M-N)$
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.						
[CoL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂]	210d	10.53	10.515	9.76	9.93	4.90	8.0	1210	3250	425	515
[CoL ₂ Py ₂]	192	11.21	11.29	10.48	10.54	5.0	8.5	1210	3280	430	515
[CoL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	205	11.27	11.38	10.51	10.78	4.95	10.0	1210	3260	420	510
[CuL ₂ Q ₂]	187	9.88	10.30	8.74	8.80	1.82	9.8	1210	3250	440	510
[CuL ₂ Py ₂]	173	11.85	11.90	10.26	10.45	1.80	8.8	1210	3250	430	505
[CuL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂]	192	11.15	11.47	9.86	9.98	1.75	10.5	1210	3250	430	500
[ZnL ₂ Q ₂]	169d	10.34	10.20	8.65	8.29	—	7.5	1210	3260	425	510
[ZnL ₂ Py ₂]	202	12.07	12.09	9.47	9.85	—	10.2	1210	3250	420	510
[ZnL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	189d	12.56	12.63	10.32	10.65	—	8.7	1210	3245	430	505

Q=quinoline, Py=pyridine, DEA=diethylamine, γ -Pic.= γ -picoline, d=decomposition

bonding at the nitrogen of the primary amino group. Most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands have been modified in the complexes proving indirect evidence of their presence as coordinated ligands. This has been further substituted⁶ by the observation of $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ around $\sim 430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively which provide the direct evidence for the formation of metal chelates and their base adducts.

The cobalt(II) complexes in DMF solution give rise to two absorption bands with maxima at 8.6 and 19.7 K.K. region which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. These absorption bands, extinction coefficients and μ_{eff} values indicate a high-spin octahedral configuration. The copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band centered at 15.0 K.K. Though three transitions ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_1(\nu_1)$, ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\nu_2)$ and ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2E(\nu_3)$ occur in Cu(II) complexes of D_{2h} symmetry due to Jahn-Teller distortions, they are often very close in energy and give rise to a single broad band envelop.

Zinc(II) complexes have presumably an octahedral configuration on the basis of their analysis, conductance and IR spectral data.

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